

WHAT IS THE PARTY ALL ABOUT?

What are you celebrating at this moment and why are you celebrating?

People make parties because they have a successful event or the other to celebrate about, no matter what the causes that come your way at the overcoming end you need to celebrate.

Celebrating is to show joy and happiness when something happens while some go for parties to also celebrate others. Even when people die some make parties for them to show their kind heart towards the things they have done when they were alive.

Let's look at the things people generate/celebrate parties for;

- **Birthday:** Birthdays are great ways of celebrating something unique that another human has done by being born into the world. They don't necessarily need to have achieved anything in their life yet, but just by coming into this world, they have brought hope into other people's lives regardless of them knowing it or not. That is why birthdays because every life has value, and so does everyone else's by association through another person's birthday.
- **Graduation:** Graduation is another occasion that is worth celebrating. Graduations are students who have put in the necessary effort to receive their degree. This is a fantastic achievement no matter what subject or qualification was achieved. Once again, it doesn't need to be anything very extravagant but just something that can be looked back on with pride and happiness at a later date when they reminisce about the occasion they graduated from university, college or school with whatever degree/qualification they received.
- **Sport:** Sporting events are also worth celebrating. It takes mental strength, physical training and lots of effort to become good at most sports. So when people do achieve their goals, they deserve to be celebrated for what they want to share with others. It is their moment to shine, so why not be there to support them so that the memory will last forever through pictures, videos and word of mouth?

However, this does not mean that every single thing in life should be celebrated. Therefore, you need balance in your life today, or you can find yourself overwhelmed just trying to keep up with everything that needs marking, which isn't healthy for anyone, let alone yourself.

- **Holidays:** Holidays are also occasions worth celebrating. After putting in work every single day of the year, whether you realise it or not, people need a break from their daily lives at times just for a short while so they can relax and recuperate enough to continue their work and daily lives with a fresh perspective and more energy than they otherwise would have had. If someone were to celebrate every holiday, it wouldn't be much of an

occasion since they occur so often throughout the year, which is why we only celebrate special holidays such as Easter, Christmas with real Christmas trees, and New Year.

- **Weddings:** Weddings are occasions that are celebrated out of pure happiness for a couple who have committed to sharing the rest of their lives. It is a celebration of something incredible happening in someone's life. It deserves to be celebrated with a party or some formal get-together where friends and family can show support.
- **Funeral:** On the other hand, funerals usually happen when people lose somebody close to them from death, which dampens the mood considerably from any celebrations going on beforehand. This can be said even more when somebody young dies at a young age where the pain is still fresh. Funerals are necessary, though, to celebrate somebody's life that has passed on with support from family and friends because that person's life had value too, which needs to be remembered in times of sorrow.

Therefore, celebrating life is what makes it worth living, so if anything, these occasions only come around when they are needed most for when people need cheering up. It may be sad when they do go away, but when all is said and done, these occasions will only hold special memories that stay with us forever through word of mouth or photos/videos that can be passed down to children or grandchildren in the future.

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